

Determination of pK_a Values of Hydrochlorides of Organic Bases in Aqueous Ethanol

(Mrs.) Usha P. Kamat*, P. V. Kamat and M. G. Datar

Monosubstituted anilines were made to react with hydrochloric acid gas to form the corresponding salts. These salts were isolated, purified and analysed for their purity. The conductance of free base and its salt solution of known strengths was determined¹ by Student-type-Cambridge conductometer, at 27° in 1 : 1 ethanol-water (v/v) as solvent medium. The data obtained was treated in usual manner² to get the pK_a values of the respective salts. A set of values thus calculated for one series is reported in Table 1. The results under the most identical conditions reported by other workers along with our results are mentioned in Table 2 (column 2 : our values).

DISCUSSION

Caska and Grunwald³ have reported the K_i (ionization) and K_d (dissociation) values of acetates of various organic bases in aqueous methanol and ethanol. Their results and those of Denison and Ramsey⁴ give the sequence of these constants as $m\text{-CH}_3 \approx p\text{-CH}_3 > m\text{-OCH}_3 \approx p\text{-OCH}_3 > m\text{-Cl} \approx p\text{-Cl}$. The results obtained in the present case (see Table 2, column 2) for hydrochlorides resemble the order, viz., $m\text{-OCH}_3 \approx p\text{-OCH}_3 > m\text{-Cl} \approx p\text{-Cl}$. The constants for the methyl-substituted isomers show some deviation, i.e., the $p\text{-CH}_3 \approx o\text{-CH}_3 > m\text{-CH}_3$, as contrary to that of the earlier workers⁴.

The stability of complexes of cadmium salts with anilinium ions show increase in e.m.f. order as $o\text{-CH}_3 > o\text{-OCH}_3 > \text{aniline} > p\text{-CH}_3 > p\text{-OCH}_3$, and the plots of $\log \beta/pK_a$ were linear⁵. The data reported by Annick de Courville and Peltier⁶ for meta- and para-substituted anilinium ions in 1% ethanol gives closer resemblance. The marginal deviations are mainly due to the difference in the solvent compositions causing minor changes in solvent and solute activities—a factor not taken into account. Michael Lucas⁷

* Present Address : CIBA Research Centre, Bombay 63, India.

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TABLE 1

pKa of chloroaniline hydrochlorides

Cell constant = C = 0.6826 temp. = 27° ethanol : water = 1 : 1

$$K_1 = C/R \quad \Lambda_v = \frac{1000K}{N} \quad \Lambda'_v = \frac{1000K}{N} \quad x = \frac{\Lambda_v - \Lambda'_v}{\Lambda_v'' - \Lambda'_v} \quad Ka = \frac{x^2c}{1-x}$$

Normality	Resistance	$K \times 10^4$	Λ_v	Λ'_v	$\Lambda_v - \Lambda'_v$	$\Lambda_v'' - \Lambda'_v$	$x \times 10^2$	(1-x)	$Ka \times 10^4$	pKa
<i>o</i> -Chloroaniline										
1/32	225.0	30.34	97.07							
1/64	392.2	17.41	111.40							
1/128	713.3	9.57	122.50							
<i>o</i> -Chloroaniline—HCl										
1/32	300.0	22.76		72.80	24.27	320.20	7.578	0.9242	1.942	3.7117
1/64	538.6	12.68		81.12	30.28	317.88	9.523	0.9048	1.566	3.8052
1/128	1092.6	6.248		79.98	42.52	321.02	13.240	0.8676	1.581	3.8013
									mean =	3.77
<i>m</i> -Chloroaniline										
1/32	326.6	20.90	66.88							
1/64	548.2	12.46	79.69							
1/128	974.8	7.002	89.62							
<i>m</i> -Chloroaniline—HCl										
1/32	458.5	14.89		47.63	19.05	345.37	5.576	0.9442	1.007	3.9970
1/64	915.6	7.456		47.72	31.97	351.28	9.101	0.9090	1.423	3.8446
1/128	1746.5	3.909		50.03	39.59	350.97	11.28	0.8872	1.120	3.9506
									mean =	3.93
<i>p</i> -chloroaniline										
1/32	380.9	17.93	57.35							
1/64	669.1	10.21	65.30							
1/128	1168.5	5.839	74.74							
<i>p</i> -chloroaniline—HCl										
1/32	540.4	12.63		40.42	16.93	352.58	4.803	0.9520	7.573	4.1207
1/64	1029.0	6.634		42.46	22.84	356.54	6.407	0.9359	6.855	4.1640
1/128	1990.0	3.430		43.90	30.84	357.10	8.630	0.9137	6.368	4.1960
									mean =	4.16

TABLE 2

pKa values of hydrochlorides of substituted anilinium ions

Anilinium ion	Values obtained in 50% EtOH	pKa values	pKa values in 1% EtOH	pKa values in 50% MeOH	pKa values aqueous medium	pKa values aqueous medium
		Ref. 11	Ref. 6	Ref. 9	Ref. 12	Ref. 13, 14
H	4.83	4.60	4.63	3.99	1.80	4.60
<i>o</i> -CH ₃	5.38	4.44	—	—	4.31	4.45
<i>m</i> -CH ₃	4.98	4.72	4.72	—	4.15	4.71
<i>p</i> -CH ₃	5.48	5.08	5.08	—	3.72	5.08
<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	5.11	4.52	—	—	4.52	—
<i>m</i> -OCH ₃	4.87	4.23	4.23	—	4.10	4.20
<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	4.81	5.34	5.36	—	5.00	5.56
<i>o</i> -Cl	3.77	2.34	—	2.23	2.58	—
<i>m</i> -Cl	3.93	3.52	3.52	3.04	3.30	3.52
<i>p</i> -Cl	4.16	3.98	3.95	3.57	3.95	4.14

has correlated the variation of these constants with the solubility in different solvent compositions. The variation in the ionization constants of the aromatic amines is equally due to the entropy and the enthalpy factors, solvation of the amine cations, and the π -electron energy changes accompanying their dissociation⁸. The data in 50% methanol⁹ could be reviewed for comparing the effect of the medium. The pK_a of chloro-substituted anilines in methanol are much lower than in other media mentioned. The proton dissociation of anilinium ions in aqueous solution is an iso-electronic reaction and is affected to a relatively minor extent¹⁰, but the same is enhanced greatly in aqueous ethanol medium, indicated by the increase in the magnitude of the pK_a values. The effect of ethanol on dissociation constants is considerably more and is in the same direction as that of methanol. The solvent composition acts as an additive factor in the dissociation of primary amines. It is also true that the electrostatic effect is the predominant factor in determining the strength of the anilinium ions but subordinate. The difference between the electrostatic and the total effect of substituents is greatest in those cases in which the resonance interaction of the groups has already been identical by consideration of dipole moment data.

Department of Chemistry,
Institute of Science,
Bombay 32, India.

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